

Reforms and Changes to Recover Traditional Craftsmanship

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Annotation: This article provides information about the development of national and traditional crafts in our country during the years of independence and the attention paid to it at the state level. The article also provides information on the legal foundations of the development of national crafts.

Keywords: national crafts, traditional crafts, local industry, UN, "craftsman", creative associations, "initiative".

INTRODUCTION

After Uzbekistan gained its independence, a new era began in the development of handicrafts, as in all areas, folk handicrafts were revived on the basis of market rules [6.213]. As a result of the first privatization of local industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan, small state-owned enterprises were transformed into private enterprises of craftsmen, new handicraft enterprises were opened. These actions were a great result for a country that has just gained independence and has not yet created enough jobs. Because the employment of the population will be improved through the development of traditional handicrafts. Crafts began to work not only for the domestic market, but also for export. The organizational form of handicrafts also changed: it was developing in the form of a small family enterprise, individual labor activity. On October 24-25, 1995, the 1st Republic Fair of Folk Craftsmen and Craftsmen of Uzbekistan was held in practical cooperation with the UN Permanent Mission in Uzbekistan. In 1997, the "Usto" creative production union of the masters of folk arts and crafts of the republic was established. The decree of the first President of the Republic Islam Karimov dated March 31, 1997 "On measures to support the further development of folk arts and crafts and applied arts through the state" and other measures are important for the revival and further development of crafts in Uzbekistan, as well as for the revival of some of its forgotten types. it has been.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Craftsmen first entered the Chamber of Goods Manufacturers of Uzbekistan, then the Chamber of Commerce and Industry. They were merged into a special organization - "Hunarmand" Republican Association. Craftsmen take part in the national competition "Tashabbus" of entrepreneurs, artisans and farms held annually in Uzbekistan. During 1996-2005, 10 artisans were recognized as winners of the "Initiative" competition for their achievements in folk crafts.

Preservation of the ancient and rich national craft history of Uzbekistan, the traditions of its unique schools preserved to this day, and the works of applied arts and crafts, wide promotion at the international level, scientific study and Many things are being done by our state in order to pass it on to the next generation, as well as to create sufficient conditions in this regard. Of course, these efforts were not in vain. Through the adopted laws and decisions, significant work has been done in the development of traditional and national handicrafts.

As we know, during the three thousand years of history of our country, various forms of folk crafts and traditional crafts have been developed. Various forms of traditional crafts have been developed in all peoples who have lived in our country since ancient times. Through these types of crafts, ancient peoples made necessary household appliances and work tools. As time passed, both the technologies of making handicrafts and the experience of the craftsmen-masters who made them increased. Also, each craftsman used to put his name and similar important symbols on the handicraft products he made. Handicrafts also had symbols reflecting the history and traditions of each nation. It follows that craft products are also an important source in the study of history. Because in telling history, we can cite many examples of handicrafts found during archaeological excavations. After gaining the independence of our country, special attention is being paid to the development of traditional crafts and the creation of its legal foundations.

One of the important conditions for the transition to market relations is the creation of a multi-level economy, that is, different forms of ownership. "Solving the issue of ownership serves as the cornerstone of the entire system of activities aimed at creating a market"[2.43]. Islam Abduganiyevich Karimov, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This is one of the urgent issues of great importance in countries that have chosen the path of market relations after the established Soviet system. By solving this issue, an important step was taken in the formation and development of a new society and new economic relations.

In the years of independence, unique changes occurred in handicrafts, like all industries, and the decree of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 27, 1991 "On the removal of creative associations, voluntary societies and foundations from the control of the party" [3] and as a result of the decrees "On creation of the fund of creators of Uzbekistan"[4] creative associations, societies, their departments and enterprises operating in the territory of Uzbekistan were also removed from the party's control.

In particular, according to the Presidential Decree "On the establishment of the State "local industry" corporation"[4] dated September 3, 1992, the enterprises that are part of the Republic's folk arts and crafts industry-trade association and the State "local industry" corporation and Organizations were transformed into the industrial and trade concern of the Republic of Folk Arts and Crafts. As a result, it became important to further improve the organization of the management of the local industry of the Republic, to expand the economic independence of enterprises in the wide introduction of market relations in the network, to increase the volume of production of consumer goods, folk arts and crafts, and to develop their initiative and entrepreneurship. For this purpose, the goal was to introduce comprehensive use of local raw materials and employment of the population [5.222].

On March 31, 1997, the Decree of the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to support the further development of folk arts and applied arts by means of the state" was issued.

According to him, in order to increase the importance of folk arts and crafts in the development of national culture, to restore the centuries-old traditions and unique types of high-quality handicrafts made by hand, and to provide state support to folk craftsmen to provide local raw materials, materials, tools, and small mechanized tools to folk craftsmen who produce high-quality artistic products, to sell finished products, to hold exhibitions and auctions tasks such as organizing a network of specialized stores and kiosks were defined [6.15]. Through these actions, a number of practical works on folk handicrafts were carried out in our country. In particular, women were involved in the production of handicraft products. As a result, handicrafts such as carpet making, hat making, satin and adras, which are suitable for women, have developed further and a specific legal basis for their development has been created.

As a result of comprehensive measures implemented for the development of national handicrafts, folk artistic and applied arts, and comprehensive support for industry representatives, the number of master craftsmen in our country has increased by 7 times and apprentices by 9 times in the last five years. the number of people employed in the industry reached 230,000.

A national catalog of folk arts of artisans was created, and 340 masters who won honorary and international exhibitions and competitions were included in this catalog. Also, about 1,500 artisans have been included in the tourism register and are contributing to the development of this industry.

At the same time, it is required to take additional measures to make full use of unused opportunities through neighborhood work, to further expand the system of exchange of experience among craftsmen, and to find new markets for handicraft products [1.].

CONCLUSION

Development of national handicrafts, folk art and applied arts in our country, thereby fully preserving the rich cultural heritage and historical traditions of our nation, widely involving the unemployed population, especially young people, women and low-income families in handicrafts in order to ensure their employment through: the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the "Hunarmand" association, the Ministry of Culture, the State Committee for the Development of Tourism to specialize the republican areas in the main directions of handicraft activities and to export handicraft products to them Proposals were made to attach the diplomatic missions of the Republic of Uzbekistan abroad in order to facilitate the demonstration and sale in foreign markets. As a result of the above efforts, the development of national crafts in our country has significantly developed.

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